

1 **TIGIT expression in natural killer cells is associated with the stem cell gene expression program.**

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6 Following chronic viral infection or encounter with the tumor microenvironment in humans with cancer,
7 immune cells enter a dysfunctional state known as exhaustion. Exhausted cells express a specific
8 repertoire of receptors at the cell surface that includes PD-1 (CD274), TIM-3 (HAVCR2) and TIGIT. We
9 studied the gene expression programs of natural killer by measuring total transcription in cells expressing
10 high or low levels of TIGIT. We found a relationship between surface expression of TIGIT and the stem
11 cells: cells expressing high levels of TIGIT at the surface were depleted for multiple stem cell
12 transcriptional features. TIGIT expression in NK cells was negatively correlated with stemness. The stem
13 cell surface marker CD44, the pluripotency factor LIF and FLT receptor ligand KIT were each expressed in
14 a graded fashion at decreased quantity with increasing TIGIT expression. However, TIGIT^{lo} cells were
15 positive for expression of a component of the pluripotency nuclear cocktail that is sufficient for induction of
16 pluripotency in fibroblasts (OSKM), MYC, and expressed high levels of a subunit of a stem cell-enriched
17 epigenetic complex (PRC2) the histone methyltransferase EZH2, and expression of MYC and EZH2 was
18 even higher in TIGIT^{hi} NK cells. The relationship between the stem cell gene expression program and
19 TIGIT surface expression in the immune system occurred in tandem with an observed and significant
20 correlation between TIGIT expression and proliferative capacity (cell cycle). Together we describe an
21 essential relationship between characteristic attributes of the embryonic stem cell and the exhaustion
22 receptor TIGIT. Thus, within the family of immune receptors that function in exhaustion, association with
23 the stem cell program is a quality specific to TIGIT, or surface receptors expressed in exhausted cells in
24 the immune system are universally associated with some level of embryonic or pluripotent quality.
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